

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Multifunctional composite materials, in which additional functions exist beyond the primary structural function, offer broad scope for system-level performance enhancements. Key functions targeted for composite structures include thermal management, self-healing, and structural health monitoring capabilities. Aerospace and other advanced composites applications, which will benefit from these capabilities, are increasingly being manufactured via Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) but the lack of available material systems suitable for AFP hinders the manufacture of these multifunctional features.

In this work, we present efforts to create prepreg materials suitable for AFP processing and to characterize the resulting structures' multifunctional performance. Specifically, the material systems explored include sacrificial filament prepreps and carbon nanotube (CNT)-containing prepreps. These materials are targeted for microvascular-based thermal management and self-healing, as well as structural health monitoring of composites, respectively. The structures are fabricated at Aurora Flight Science's facility with an Electroimpact AFP machine.

Sacrificial filaments, which degrade in a post-cure cycle to embed hollow synthetic microvascular networks within a composite structure, are extruded in continuous lengths suitable for spooling onto unidirectional carbon fiber prepreps or for subsequent 3D printing directly onto the prepreg surfaces. AFP-related parameters, such as feeding and roller pressures, are correlated with filament quality and ultimate thermal management and healing functionality. Finally, vertically-aligned carbon nanotubes are transferred onto AFP-ready prepreg for damage sensing and resistive heating applications. The quality of interfacial bonding and maintenance of vertical CNT orientation during AFP lay-up is investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite materials exhibit high stiffness- and strength-densities that enable heavier metallic components to be replaced with lighter composite materials. However, efforts to further enhance the performance and capabilities of structures such as aircraft often result in the integration of additional components and/or materials that negate the weight savings offered by composite materials. For example, additional mechanisms (e.g. Electro-Mechanical Expulsion De-icing Systems (EMEDS) or pneumatic boots) are installed for de-icing applications, or extra layers of material are added to a design to account for the limited damage tolerance of composite materials. Thus, designers and manufacturers seek multifunctional composite materials that can improve performance without sacrificing weight and structural properties.

Key functions targeted for composite structures include thermal management, self-healing, and structural health monitoring capabilities. Various approaches have been utilized to achieve these

capabilities [1-4], including sacrificial filaments and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) integrated with CFRP prepreg materials for microvascular-based thermal management and self-healing, as well as structural health monitoring, respectively. However, the integration of these features with CFRP prepregs has generally been time-consuming and expensive, and limited to the scale of small laboratory specimens. Schemes for automated, scalable manufacture of multifunctional fiber-reinforced composites have been lacking.

In this work, multifunctional CFRP specimens are created via automated, additive manufacturing processes including Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) and 3D printing. Specifically, sacrificial filament prepregs and carbon nanotube (CNT)-containing prepregs are studied for thermal management, self-healing, and structural health monitoring applications. Both autoclave and out-of-autoclave (OoA) thermoset epoxy material systems are explored.

2 METHODS, ASSUMPTIONS, AND PROCEDURES

Included in its manufacturing facilities, Aurora Flight Sciences utilizes an Electroimpact 7-axis high-rail gantry AFP system (Figure 1) for the high rate, high quality production of manned and unmanned aircraft components. The AFP head supports 16 spools of 12.7 mm (0.25 inch) wide thermoset prepreg slit tape. In this work, the prepreg slit tape is used as a carrier for multifunctional components including sacrificial filaments and CNTs. Two different commercial aerospace-grade prepreg material systems were used; Hexcel's 8552 autoclave-cure thermoset epoxy was used with AS4 unidirectional carbon fiber for the thermal management applications, while Cytec's 5320-1 OoA thermoset epoxy was used with IM7 unidirectional carbon fiber for self-healing and structural health monitoring applications.

Figure 1: Aurora's AFP machine with 16-spool head for 12.7 mm width slit tape.

2.1 Extrusion of Sacrificial Filaments

The fabrication of embedded microvascular features is achieved by sacrificial filaments, which are thermoplastic filaments with an embedded catalyst that promotes depolymerization into a gaseous form at elevated temperatures. This transformation leaves embedded channel features that correspond to the position of the initial sacrificial filament. Hence, these sacrificial filaments define the final diameter and network trajectory of the channel pathways through which fluids will flow for thermal management and self-healing applications.

The fabrication of microvascular composites using AFP requires continuous sacrificial filaments of substantial length. Furthermore, for scalable, commercial applications, the elevated temperatures that promote depolymerization will ideally be slightly greater than the cure temperature of the resin system, while requiring minimal time to fully depolymerize. In this work, a single screw extruder at the University of Massachusetts Lowell (UMass Lowell) Department of Plastics Engineering was used to continuously melt-extrude polylactide (PLA) sacrificial filaments (1.4 km/hour) with 3 wt% tin (II) oxalate catalyst. The composition was slightly modified for the extrusion-based process, as 1 wt% mineral oil was added to function as a binder between the PLA pellets and the tin (II) oxalate catalyst. The extruded filaments pass through a water-cooling bath to solidify the molten strands and then pulled through a belt puller to be spooled by an automatic spooler, as shown schematically in Figure 2.

The diameter of the extruded filament can be tailored to the intended application, ranging from 150 μm to 1.75 mm. The melt-extrusion process is demonstrated to improve the kinetics and reproducibility of the thermal depolymerization process relative to chemical treatment methods of fabricating sacrificial filaments. The chemical treatment process has depolymerization times ranging from 24-48 hours at 200°C [5], while the metered amount of catalyst and its improved dispersion within the melt extrusion system results in depolymerization times between 12 and 24 hours. Moreover, the probability of successful evacuation of embedded channels is increased by this method.

Figure 2: Schematic of PLA filament extrusion set-up.

2.2 Integration of Sacrificial Filaments with Prepreg

The manufacture of large-scale microvascular composite structures via AFP requires material formats compatible with little-to-no modification of the existing equipment. Hence, the team needed a method to integrate the extruded, spooled sacrificial filaments onto the 12.7 mm wide prepreg slit tape for loading on the AFP head. A roll-to-roll continuous spooling apparatus was developed to rapidly integrate the sacrificial filaments with the slit tape. The apparatus un-spools the unidirectional prepreg slit tape and sacrificial filaments (right-hand side of Figure 3). These materials are joined and compacted within a compression roller in the central portion of the apparatus. A motor (left-hand side of Figure 3) rotates a take-up spool at 7.5 meters per minute (300 inches per minute), onto which the combined and compacted materials are re-spooled. As the prepreg is pulled through the apparatus, an indexer spool governs the horizontal pattern to wind the prepreg evenly onto the take-up spool.

Figure 3: Apparatus to spool sacrificial filaments onto prepreg slit tape.

Nevertheless, this approach of integrating sacrificial filaments with prepreg slit tape for AFP had some drawbacks. In terms of the design of microvascular networks, the orientation and start/end positions of the sacrificial filaments are limited to the orientation and start/end position of the slit tape being laid down via AFP. In addition, the rollers within the AFP head that pinch the slit tape and advance its position to the compaction roller have a maximum 400 μm (0.4 mm) gap between them. This gap limits the diameter of the sacrificial filaments that can be spooled together with the slit tape,

which may have a thickness of 200 μm (0.2 mm) or more. As the material is fed through the AFP head, many of the PLA filaments would extend into a wave feature, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Defects in sacrificial filaments as material is fed through AFP head.

2.3 3D Printing of Microvascular Channels

As a result of the issues encountered with sacrificial filaments spooled directly onto prepreg tows, an alternate approach was utilized to pattern the PLA-catalyst fibers onto the carbon prepreg slit tape. The melt-extruded, spooled sacrificial filament is fed through a 3D print-head which can print microvascular network features directly onto the slit tape (Figure 5(b)). This approach enables more precise control and design flexibility with regard to the orientation, size, and positioning of the microvascular channels, which are now independent of the orientation and positioning of the underlying unidirectional slit tape.

To demonstrate this approach, a MendelMax 2.0 3D printer, shown in Figure 5(a), was used. The 3D printer reads STL files exported from a Computer Aided Design (CAD) program and interprets the geometry as a series of motion commands. The printing process feeds the sacrificial thermoplastic filament (i.e., PLA treated with Tin (II) Oxalate) into the printer head, or “hot end”, that heats the plastic to its melting point (200°C for PLA) and extrudes the material through the nozzle orifice. The necessary feature dimensions are dictated by the feed rate into the print-head and the translation rate relative to the substrate. These parameters are calculated via a software algorithm, but can be manually modified for non-standard feature dimensions.

Figure 5: (a) MendelMax 2.0 3D printer used and (b) sacrificial thermoplastic material printed directly onto prepreg slit tape.

2.4 CNT Fabrication

Vertically-aligned CNTs (VACNTs) were obtained from N12 Technologies, Inc. (Cambridge, MA) on silicon wafers. In the current work, the VACNTs were transferred from the silicon wafers to the prepreg slit tape using a transfer-printing process that involves heat and pressure. However, N12 is also capable of continuously growing VACNTs on a catalyst coated metal substrate and subsequently transferring the VACNTs to prepreg slit tape spools (shown in Figure 6(a) on a 2-meter long tow) while maintaining vertical alignment, as shown in the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image in Figure 6(b). When laid down by AFP, the VACNTs essentially “stitch” adjacent layers together and reinforce the interlaminar region. The increased electrical and thermal conductivity of the VACNTs also enables structural health monitoring via infrared thermography, as discussed in Section 3.2.

Figure 6: (a) Continuous transfer of VACNTs onto prepreg slit tape and (b) SEM image showing vertical alignment of VACNTs after transfer to prepreg.

2.5 Specimens for Characterization of Multifunctional Performance

2.5.1 Thermal Management Applications

A total of four microvascular composite panels were fabricated via AFP using the AS4/8552 autoclave-cure material system, and pre-spoiled with PLA sacrificial filament. Each panel measured 40 cm long by 40 cm wide. The vascular geometry consisted of 500 µm diameter headers and footers connected to a set of 300 µm diameter stringers in a 4-layer pattern shown in Figure 7 to represent standard heat exchanger configurations and to enable fluid flow for thermal load dissipation. Four additional layers of unidirectional prepreg slit tape were laid on top, producing 8-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ structures.

During autoclave cure, the intersecting PLA fibers were fused together [6] to create an interconnected network. After autoclave cure, the PLA fibers were evacuated by placing the panels in a vacuum oven at 200°C under 95 kPa of pressure for 24-48 hours. Syringe tips with 360 µm diameter were used to attach 3.175 mm inner diameter tubing to the edges of the composite plates to enable fluid flow through the microchannels and verification of full PLA evacuation.

Figure 7: Microvascular composite plates fabricated for thermal management applications.

2.5.2 Self-Healing & Damage Detection Applications

Additional specimens were fabricated using the IM7/5320-1 OoA material system to evaluate the damage detection and self-healing capabilities offered by microvascular channels and VACNTs. Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens were fabricated for subsequent testing of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. The microchannels in the DCB specimens were printed directly onto the prepreg surface on a 3-D printer and had rectangular cross-sectional dimensions of 1 mm wide by 0.4 mm (400 μm) high. As summarized in Table 1, a total of three batches of DCB specimens were fabricated. The first batch consisted of baseline specimens in which neither VACNTs nor microvascular channels were embedded. The second batch was fabricated with embedded microvascular channels at the mid-plane. These specimens would indicate the potential degradation of fracture toughness due to the presence of microchannels relative to the baseline specimens. In addition the healing efficiency of a healing chemistry (two-part epoxy/amine supplied by Miller-Stephenson, consisting of epoxy Epon 862 and amine (i.e. hardener) Epikure 3046) could be evaluated by these specimens. Finally, the third batch includes both microchannels and VACNTs. The purpose of these specimens was to evaluate whether the VACNTs could restore the fracture toughness degraded by the presence of the microchannels, and if the VACNTs could further accelerate the healing process by providing enhanced thermal conductivity. In addition, the VACNTs could be used to potentially detect damage in the specimens.

Batch	Reason	Samples
Baseline	Test effect of channels on fracture toughness	Baseline-1
		Baseline-2
		Baseline-3
		Baseline-5
PLA	Create channels for Self-healing	PLA-1
		PLA-3
		PLA-4
		PLA-5
PLA & CNT	Offset loss in fracture toughness & potentially promote self-healing	CNT-1
		CNT-3
		CNT-4

Table 1: Test matrix of DCB samples created, and sample names.

Three plates were manufactured using 26 plies through the thickness (~ 4 mm) and 12 tows wide (~ 152 mm). The length of each plate was approximately 177 mm. The mid-plane resided between the 13th and 14th plies, where a non-porous Teflon sheet was placed at the front edge of the plate to create the pre-crack required by ASTM standard D 5528-13. The baseline plate comprised solely of unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg slit tape, the PLA plate containing a microvascular network at the mid-plane of the layup, and the CNT sample contained both a microvascular network and one layer of VACNTs at the mid-plane of the layup. Figure 8(a) shows an image of the VACNTs transferred to prepreg; the VACNTs can be seen as the darker black sections within the boxed region. Figure 8(b) shows the Teflon sheet and the 3D printed microchannels. The final DCB specimens prior to PLA depolymerization are shown in Figure 8(c).

Figure 8: (a) Middle ply of PLA & CNT samples before addition of PLA channels. (b) Middle ply in layup with printed PLA features. (c) DCB specimens prior to filament evacuation (25 mm scale bar).

The PLA was evacuated from the DCB specimens to create the hollow microchannels. Three specimens per evacuation cycle were loaded in a vacuum oven at 200°C and 95 kPa of vacuum for 24-48 hours. X-ray MicroCT images such as the one shown in Figure 9 showed that some of the channels were not sufficiently evacuated after one 24-hour cycle, thus requiring a second heating cycle. After evacuating the PLA from the microchannels, hinges were bonded using a cyanoacrylate adhesive (Krazy Glue) to the top and bottom surfaces of each specimen at the pre-crack edge in preparation for DCB testing. In addition, 25 mm wide copper tape was wrapped around the ends of each PLA and PLA/CNT specimen in order to connect leads for resistive heating. The copper tape was applied at the back edge and around each arm at the front of the DCB. The edges of the copper tape were adhered to the specimen surface using a conductive graphite loaded epoxy to ensure a sufficient electrical and mechanical connection. Finally, two coats of typewriter correction fluid were applied to one side of each specimen to aid in the visualization of crack propagation as per the ASTM standard cited previously. A fully fabricated DCB specimen is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: X-ray MicroCT image showing incomplete evacuation of PLA after one heating cycle.

Figure 10: Fully fabricated DCB specimen (25 mm bar for scale)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal Management

A setup to flow fluid through the microvascular composite plates was devised according to the diagram in Figure 11. The rotary gear pump was maintained at a pressure of about 193 kPa, measured by a flow controller immediately downstream of the pump, to ensure that fluid would not leak from the fittings. The composite plate rested on a piece of insulation foam to minimize heat transfer through the bottom face. The outlet was positioned over a beaker atop a mass balance to measure the average flow rate. Parallel to the inlet flow was a fan that was used to provide forced convection over the top surface of the plate. An anemometer was used to determine the fan air speeds at the plate. Not pictured in Figure 11 is the FLIR thermal imaging camera, which was situated directly above the plate to collect images of the plate surface.

Figure 11: Thermal performance test set-up

Figure 12 shows thermal images of a single microvascular composite plate at three different fan air speed settings and for an average fluid flow rate of 14.4 mL/min. The temperature scale bar is consistent over the three images and the contours correspond to surface temperatures of the top plate surface. As shown, the heat transfer is increased and the surface temperatures decrease as the fan speed increases from 0 m/s to 1.38 m/s due to the increased heat transfer caused by the forced convection. The left-most image corresponds to a free convection condition. The fluid is clearly flowing through all of the channels and the heat is also conducting into the carbon fibre between the channels.

In the image progression from left to right, it can be seen that the spreading of heat into the carbon fiber between the channels is sharply decreased with higher air circulation rates, and the temperatures over the channels themselves are also slightly decreased. Especially noticeable is the flow disparity between the channels. This disparity is indicative of differential flow resistances between neighbouring channels, leading to a higher pressure drop and therefore non-uniform flow in the network. The source of the differential resistance could be a result of incomplete evacuation of the PLA sacrificial filaments, or deformation of the microchannels during the autoclave cure cycle.

Figure 12: Flow visualization via thermal images.

X-ray MicroCT images were taken of sections of the plate to investigate the cause for disparity in fluid flow between multiple stringers/microchannels. As indicated by Figure 13(a), specimens were cut from Stringer #2 (less flow) and Stringer #3 (greater flow) to compare differences in the cross-sectional area of the two stringers under X-ray MicroCT. Post-processing the CT images (Figure 13(b)), the cross-sectional area of Stringer #2 was measured to be approximately 0.16 mm^2 , while the cross-sectional area of Stringer #3 was measured to be approximately 3.5 times greater at 0.55 mm^2 . Furthermore, the cross-sectional area remained fairly uniform along the length of Stringer #3, while a noticeable thinning of the area was observed in Stringer #2. This thinning was consistent with the lesser flow observed in the IR thermal images along the length of Stringer #2. The larger, more uniform cross-sectional area of Stringer #3 explains the improved fluid flow through Stringer #3 relative to Stringer #2.

Another interesting observation was the relatively rough interior walls of the channels (Figure 13 (c)). The wall roughness can also affect the ability of the fluid to flow through the channels. This wall roughness may have a result of the fact that the matrix may not have fully gelled by the time it had reached a high enough temperature for the sacrificial filament to either melt or decompose.

Figure 13: (a) IR thermal image of microvascular plate showing fluid flow disparities in stringers; (b) X-ray MicroCT images of two stringers showing differences in cross-sectional areas; (c) axial view from X-ray MicroCT image of a microchannel showing interior wall roughness.

3.2 Self-Healing and Damage Detection

The self-healing performance of the IM7/5320-1 composite DCB specimens was evaluated via Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests in which the two arms of the DCB are translated

vertically at a rate of 2 mm/min to propagate the mid-plane delamination crack by a horizontal distance of 50 mm, as shown in Figure 14(a). The embedded microchannels were pre-filled with the liquid healing agents prior to complete crack propagation using a syringe. During crack propagation, the liquid healing agents diffusively mix to initiate the self-healing polymerization reaction. This reaction can be accelerated by heat, thereby reducing the required healing time. The specimens were resistively heated by connecting alligator clips to the copper tape leads. A total power of 20 Watts was applied across each sample for two hours to heat the specimens to approximately 110°C, thereby accelerating the self-healing process. A FLIR thermal image camera was used to measure the thermal profile, as shown in Figure 14(b).

Figure 14: (a) DCB specimen during Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test; (b) Thermal image of cracked DCB specimen showing crack front.

The healing efficiency, η , was calculated by comparing the healed Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, $K_{IC,healed}$, to the initial Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, $K_{IC, virgin}$, as shown in Equation 1. This approximately correlates to the ratio of the peak loads before fracture, assuming the crack length is roughly equal for the two peak loads.

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC,healed}}{K_{IC, virgin}} \approx \frac{P_{healed}}{P_{virgin}} \quad (1)$$

The loads (P_{healed} and P_{virgin}) at which the load-displacement curve deviates from linearity correspond to the physical onset of delamination from the Teflon insert in the interior of the specimen width. An example of a virgin and healed DCB load-displacement curve is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Example load-displacement curve for DCB virgin and healed specimens.

It was noted that the presence of the embedded 1 mm-wide x 0.4 mm-thick microchannels resulted in a 27% reduction in Mode I fracture toughness when compared to the Baseline DCB specimens.

Embedding smaller microchannels could reduce this difference in fracture toughness. Alternatively, DCB tests on the PLA/CNT specimens showed that the embedded VACNTs completely offset the reduction in Mode I fracture toughness. Rather, the VACNTs improved the fracture toughness in the mid-plane sufficiently to deflect the crack away from the mid-plane position of the microvascular features.

The average healing efficiency for 4 specimens after a single healing cycle was found to be 57%. One of the specimens was completely separated to observe the amount of healing agents in the microchannels. As shown in Figure 16(a), it was evident that there was an insufficient amount of liquid in each channel, preventing them from thoroughly mixing and curing to re-bond the DCB specimen interfaces. The microchannels in this specimen were completely filled with the two-part healing chemistry (Figure 16(b)) and re-tested a second time. The healing efficiency for this specimen during a second healing cycle was found to be 114%. This experiment demonstrated that when the microchannels are sufficiently filled with the appropriate healing agents, multiple healing cycles can occur which can help prolong the durability, damage tolerance, and reliability of a composite structure.

Figure 16: (a) Two halves of a DCB specimen showing insufficient amounts of healing agents in microchannels. (b) Microchannels completely filled with healing agents.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Material systems suited for the automated, scalable manufacture of synthetic microvascular composites were investigated for multifunctional carbon fibre-reinforced composites with autoclave and out-of-autoclave thermoset epoxy resin systems. Sacrificial fiber extrusion enables continuous, rapid production of filaments for microvasculature. Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) was demonstrated to fabricate microvascular composite heat exchanger geometries, while 3D printing was used to directly print or transfer features for microvascular self-healing composites. Dissipation of heat via microvascular heat exchanger geometries embedded within composite plates was demonstrated. 3-D printed microvascular features were demonstrated to heal interlaminar fracture damage.

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